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CITIES THROUGH
SMART DECISION
SUPPORT SYSTEMS

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Analysis tools to process data and inference rules

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Preface

This report is prepared within the framework of the OPTIMUS – OPTIMising the energy USE in cities with smart decision support system (OPTIMUS) (608703), supported by the 7th Framework Programme, under the Objective ICT-2013.6.4 Optimising Energy Systems in Smart Cities. OPTIMUS aims to design, develop and implementation a Decision Support System (DSS) addressed to city authorities, in order to assist them to optimize the energy use in their premises and reduce CO₂ emissions.

Summary

This deliverable summarizes the work carried out in Task 3.2 *Data Mining Analysis*. The purpose of this task is to develop prediction models to forecast the energy performance behaviour of buildings. Four prediction models have been devised which deal with renewable energy production, energy consumption, indoor temperature, and energy prices.

The theoretical premises of the prediction models and their implementations are outlined. The methodological approach described for every model will serve as a guide to develop new prediction models.

The prediction models are a component of the OPTIMUS DSS. The models make use of the semantic framework –developed within Task 3.1 *Semantic Framework for Data Integration*– to retrieve the data they need.

Deliverable structure

This document is divided into two main sections: formulation of the prediction models and implementation of the models.

The description of the prediction models encompasses:

- Methodological approach.
- Purpose of the model.
- Example of the implementation in real conditions.
- Description of the data required to invoke the model.

The two implementations of the model have been based on the black box and the grey box models. The implementation process involves two steps:

- Creating the prediction model: the prediction model is created based on the historical data.
- Applying the prediction model: the prediction model is deployed using monitored data to forecast the performance of the following week.

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1 Introduction

This report describes the status of the tools developed in Task 3.2 *Data Mining Analysis*. The tools developed in this task enable to forecast the energy behaviour of buildings through prediction models. The forecast has been performed based on the semantic data provided through the framework implemented in Task 3.1.

An accurate forecast of the building behaviour becomes necessary to implement the action plans proposed by the OPTIMUS DSS, such as the management of the produced energy and the scheduling of the heating and cooling systems.

A prediction model can be used to forecast data based on some input variables which can influence the future behaviour of the output data. Depending on the input data variables and on their relation with the output data, the model may be based on a simple linear equation or on a complex neural network.

The main outcomes of Task 3.2 have been four prediction models that deal with renewable energy production, energy consumption, indoor temperature, and energy prices. The methodological approach adopted to create these models can be applied to create new prediction models to be used in similar conditions with other performance indicators.

Interconnection between Tasks

The work carried out in Task 3.2 is related to other tasks in the following way:

- The prediction models use the monitored data collected and integrated through the semantic framework described in Deliverable 3.1 *Published data in an open data portal*.
- The inference rules formulated in Deliverable 3.3 use the data predicted by the models described in this document.
- The Task 3.5 *Integration and Development of OPTIMUS DSS* integrates the prediction models developed in T3.2 with the different modules of the DSS.

2 Data prediction through data mining methods

The prediction models developed for forecasting the behaviour of some indicators of a building are described in this section. The models are based on data-driven methods which can be classified into three categories, as described in Deliverable 2.1 *Overall architecture of the DSS* (in Section 2.4.2 *Predictive modules*): empirical or “black-box” methods, calibrated simulations, and “gray-box” methods.

Four prediction models have been developed dealing with renewable energy production, energy consumption, indoor temperature, and energy prices. In the following sections, each model is described in the following terms:

1. Methodological approach.
2. Purpose of the model.
3. Example of the implementation in real conditions.
4. Description of the data required to invoke the model.

2.1 Prediction model for renewable energy production

2.1.1 Methodology

An accurate forecast of the energy production from the photovoltaic panels (PV) of the OPTIMUS pilot buildings is necessary to implement the OPTIMUS DSS action plans, such as the management of produced energy and the PV maintenance.

A multiple linear regression (MLR) model is used to describe the direct or indirect influence of various variables in the PV production, as presented in the following formula.

$$\hat{y} = ax_1 + bx_2 + \dots + kx_i + \dots + x_p = y + \varepsilon$$

where:

ε is the difference between the original y and the predicted (\hat{y}) PV production and

x_i are the influential variables used

This type of model is considered as appropriate for a variety of reasons:

- Relevant literature (Almohri et al., 2014) indicates MLR models as one of the most accurate and widely used solutions in the field of energy production forecasting with numerous applications describing real life problems.
- The majority of the influential variables to be used to predict energy production (e.g. weather forecasts) have already been modelled and can be easily exploited by the forecasting models.
- MLR models can potentially provide quantitative evidence to deploy PV maintenance action plans and to manage the energy production in accordance with the observed performances.

When dealing with MLR models, the most important task is to specify the independent variables x_i (predictors/regressors) that will be used to estimate the dependent variable \hat{y} , which in the present study is the Energy Produced by the PV plant y . At an initial stage numerous variables measured on site or on nearby weather stations can be considered, such as:

- Solar radiation.
- Outdoor temperature.
- Humidity.
- Cloud cover.

It is well known that more predictors lead to less biased forecasts (better fitting) but increase at the same time the variance of the model which leads to less accurate predictions (Makridakis et al., 2008). As a result, in order to maximize the forecasting accuracy a no over-fitting model must be specified, meaning a model with few regressors but good predictability (Hyndman & Athanopoulos, 2014).

Many statistical methods and tests can be used to decide the type and number of regressors that will be included in a prediction model. The forward stepwise method (James et al., 2013) has been chosen since in cases with large sets of potential independent variables from which an adequate amount need to be extracted – like our case– it is considered as a more appropriate choice. In the literature, the backward stepwise method is mostly used for modest-sized set of potential variables that need to be eliminated and for fine-tuning existing models. The algorithm of the method used is given below, and the procedure is visualized in Figure 1.

- Let I_0 denote the null model (no predictors are included).
- For $k=0, \dots, p-1$ (p is the number of predictors).
 1. Consider all $p-k$ models that augment the predictors in I_k with one additional predictor.
 2. Choose the best among these $p-k$ models I_{k+1} using the R^2 (Pearsons correlation) as a criterion.
- Select a single best model from among I_0, \dots, I_p using the Bayesian information Criterion (BIC).

Figure 1: Left: For each of the p - k predictors the Pearson's correlation is calculated to decide which one should be included next in the l model. Right: For each of the p models produced the BIC is calculated to decide which one is the most suitable.

2.1.2 Predictive models for PV production

Two main options can be considered when dealing with MLR models to predict hourly energy production from PV:

1. Estimation of an integrated model for 24 hours round the clock, followed by disaggregation to hourly basis.
2. Creation of a separate model for each hour of the day.

The first method was initially considered, as it is less complicated and with low computational costs. However, an integrated model that produces forecasts for the whole day cannot, in practice, capture the specificities of certain hours. In this case, such specificities appear during the sunrise and sunset hours and are due to the fact that although solar radiation exists at that time, PV panels only produce energy when a significant amount of radiation is available and above a certain threshold.

As a result, the second method was selected for further development, since it was found that excellent performance could be achieved in a forecast by the hour. This way, different MLR models are calculated, each one predicting a specific hour of the day. The forecasts for each hour and day are then chronologically shorted to make a one-week-ahead forecast (168 hours).

Although new forecasts are produced on a daily basis, the MLR models are re-estimated automatically only every two months. Apart from the computational cost, updating a MLR model on a daily basis would lead to negligible changes at the coefficients of the models given that a sample of thousands of observations have been used to develop it. However, significant changes could be produced when a set of two month predictions (1440 observations, approximately) becomes available. This approach ensures that OPTIMUS DSS is always up to date without being overloaded by unnecessary model estimations.

The applied method is presented in the flow chart of Figure 2.

Figure 2: Flow chart presenting the methodology adopted in the specification of the energy production MLR models

2.1.3 Example: Sant Cugat Town Hall energy production

In the case of the Sant Cugat photovoltaic plant, 16 MLR models were calculated, each one predicting a specific hour of the day between 7:00 and 23:59. In the rest of the sample (24:00-6:59) no energy production was detected and the corresponding forecasts were manually set to zero.

The MLR models were estimated using a training sample of 1 year, as seen on Table 1. The data of one-year PV production were collected by the on-site monitoring system of the Town Hall, while the weather data was stored in the database of a nearby weather station.

Table 1: Dataset used for the Sant Cugat Town Hall

Observed period	17 th April 2014 -17 th April 2015
Frequency of measurements	1 hour
Number of measurements	2385 hours of non-zero production
PV production	Measured on site
Weather data	Collected from weather station

The symmetric Mean Absolute Percentage Error (sMAPE) across the whole sample with non-zero PV production was calculated equal to 13%, with insignificant bias to be detected. The MLR models for hours 07:00-07:59, 12:00-12:59 and 16:00-16:59 are presented below as an example, while the predicted (red line) and the original data (black line) are displayed in Figure 3 for 300 random observations of the sample.

$$\begin{aligned}
 PVproduction_{07:00-07:59} &= Constant + a * Solar\ Radiation + b * Temperature + c * Month + d \\
 &\quad * Solar\ Radiation * Month + e * Solar\ Radiation * Temperature
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 PVproduction_{12:00-12:59} &= Constant + a * Solar\ Radiation + b * (Solar\ Radiation)^2 + c \\
 &\quad * (Solar\ Radiation)^3 + d * Humidity + e * Dewpoint + f * Month + g * Month^2 \\
 &\quad + h * Month^3 + i * Solar\ Radiation * Dewpoint
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 PVproduction_{16:00-16:59} &= Constant + a * Solar\ Radiation + b * Dewpoint + c * Humidity + d * Oldness \\
 &\quad + e * Month + f * Solar\ Radiation + Month + g * Solar\ Radiation * Age + h \\
 &\quad * Humidity^2 + i * Humidity^3 + g * Dewpoint^2 + h * Dewpoint^3
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 3: The predicted (red line) and the original (black line) PV production for 300 random observations of the Sant Cugat Town Hall data set

2.1.4 Example: Savona Campus energy production

In the Savona Campus PV plant, 15 individual MLR models were calculated, each one predicting a specific hour of the day between 7:00 and 20:59. In the rest of the sample (21:00-6:59) no energy production was detected and the corresponding forecasts were manually set to zero.

The MLR models were estimated following the methodological approach presented in Section 2.1.1 and 2.1.2, using a training sample of 4 months, as seen on Table 2. The PV production data were collected by the on-site monitoring system of the campus, while the weather data was stored in the database of a nearby weather station.

Table 2: Dataset used for the Savona Campus

Observed period	1 st January 2014 - 22 th April 2015
Frequency of measurements	1 hour
Number of measurements	3338 hours of non-zero production
PV production	Measured on site
Weather data	Collected from weather station

The sMAPE across the whole sample with non-zero PV production was calculated equal to 17%, with insignificant bias to be detected. The MLR models for hours 07:00-07:59, 16:00-16:59 and 18:00-18:59 are presented below as an example, while the predicted (red line) and

the original data (black line) are displayed in Figure 4 for 168 random observations (one week) of the sample.

$$PVproduction_{07:00-07:59} = Constant + a * Solar\ Radiation + b * Solar\ Radiation^2$$

$$PVproduction_{16:00-16:59} = Constant + a * Solar\ Radiation + b * SolarRadiation^2 + c * Humidity$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 PVproduction_{18:00-18:59} \\
 = Constant + a * Month + b * Temperature + c * Humidity + d * SolarRadiation \\
 + e * Dewpoint + f * SolarRadiation^2
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 4: The predicted (red line) and the original (black line) PV production for 168 random observations of the Savona Campus data set.

2.1.5 Data required

Following the stepwise method presented in the methodological approach presented in Section 2.1.1, the best subset of regressors was selected and the model was determined. However, in order to apply this procedure a list of possible regressors was needed. To start, the list must include all weather and time variables (primary predictors) that are both available and predictable for the three pilot buildings.

An additional set of secondary predictors was produced using the primary regressors, such as their second and third power (e.g. Humidity², Humidity³) and their inter-relation (e.g. the products Temperature*Hour or Temperature*Humidity).

The main reason to introduce secondary predictors is that the linear nature of the original model (a linear relationship between the predictors and the response is assumed) cannot always describe adequately physical phenomena like PV production and energy consumption. By including powers of the primary predictors in the model, non-linearity of the data is incorporated leading to more accurate forecasts (see Figure 5). Moreover, since each variable is independent from other regressors, non-interactions can be revealed from the original MLR model. However, if both the primary predictors and their interaction are included in the model, this relationship can be estimated and taken into consideration. This is of high importance in this case since, for example, high radiation leads to high production but high temperature has the opposite result. At the same time, radiation indirectly affects the temperature of the panels. Thus, if the interrelation of these variables has not been considered, a systematic forecasting error will be observed during extreme weather conditions.

Figure 5: Left: The residuals of a MLR model used to describe a non-linear phenomenon using only primary predictors. Right: The residuals of a MLR model used to describe the same phenomenon using both primary predictors and some of their powers. As seen, the deviation of the errors has been significantly decreased.

Taking the above into consideration, a final matrix of the predictors has been developed and the stepwise method applied. A list of the primary predictors that were considered for the Sant Cugat and Savona Campus pilot building is given in Table 3, the secondary ones arise accordingly.

Table 3: List of the primary predictors for the Sant Cugat Town Hall.

Predictor	Measurement Unit	Source	Type of data
Temperature	°C	Weather station	Weather
Humidity	-	Weather station	Weather
Pressure	Pa	Weather station	Weather
Wind Direction Degrees	-	Weather station	Weather
Solar Radiation	W/m ²	Weather station	Weather
Dew point	°C	Weather station	Weather
Wind Speed	km/h	Weather station	Weather
Month	-	DSS engine	Time
Hour	-	DSS engine	Time

To ensure a good performance of the final model, a data cleansing procedure has been additionally performed before the coefficients of the model are estimated. This includes the removal of the outliers and the high leverage points through standardized residuals and the calculation of the Cook's distance to the observations. Finally, the collinearity and the statistical significance of all the variables (p-values) and the model as a whole (F-statistic) is checked and additional adjustments are performed if necessary.

The modelling and the whole forecasting procedure was performed using the R software platform (R Core Team, 2013), an open source language that during the last decades has become one of the most popular and important tools for computational statistics and data science. A fundamental advantage of R is that it is supported by a growing community of more than 2 million users and thousands of developers worldwide who have developed and distributed hundreds of open source packages. In order to build an integrated solution other advanced solutions have also been used: MASS (Venables & Ripley, 2002), car (Fox & Weisberg, 2011), glmnet (Friedman et al., 2010) and forecast (Hyndman, 2015).

2.2 Prediction model for energy consumption

2.2.1 Methodology

The methodological approach used for the prediction of electricity consumption of the whole building follows the same principles and practices described earlier in Section 2.1.1 for the PV production forecasting models.

First of all, a significant number of influential variables have been considered and tested. Apart from weather variables that were used for the prediction of PV production, additional variables

that influence significantly energy consumption are taken into consideration (e.g. indoor temperature, Heating and Cooling Degree Days, Occupancy etc.).

These variables may vary in each case study according to:

- Buildings' energy uses and occupancy patterns
- Installed monitoring systems and available data sources.

The steps to be taken to make the model are summed up as follows:

1. A list of possible influential variables-predictors is assumed (weather and building profile data).
2. The additive assumption of the model is removed by including both the main effect (predictor) and the interaction of the variables.
3. Non-linear relationships are also considered by including the powers of main variables in the model.
4. After the collection of all the possible variables, the collinear ones are excluded.
5. The predictors are chosen using the forward stepwise method.
6. The statistical significance of the remaining variables is tested and insignificant variables are excluded.
7. The statistical significance of the model as a whole is tested and appropriate changes are made if needed.
8. Given the model, outliers and high leverage points are detected and excluded from the data set.
9. The model is recalculated using the filtered data set through steps 5 to 7 so that the most appropriate coefficients become available.
10. The procedure (1-9) is applied for each hour separately. That way the special characteristics of each hour are taken into account and minimization of the forecasting errors becomes possible.
11. The procedure is applied for working days (weekdays) and non-working days (weekends-holidays) separately. This will also lead to the effects of point 10. To do so relative information (national and local holidays – schedules of the building) must become available.

The process is also presented in the flow chart of Figure 6.

Figure 6: Flow chart presenting the methodology adopted in the specification of the total energy consumption MLR models.

2.2.2 Predictive model for energy consumption

In order to model the total energy use of the building, the energy consumption data can be measured hourly and daily (Working-Non Working). This approach enables:

1. To minimize the probability of large errors due to the wrong specification of the time and the schedules of the building to occur, and
2. To obtain simplified models with limited number of regressors (Day, hour and their powers – inter effects are excluded).

Thus, the effect of the rest of the influential variables, such as Outdoor temperature and Humidity, can become clearer and be effectively estimated.

In this case 48 different MLR models were calculated, each one predicting a specific hour of the day between (from 00:00 to 23:59) for two types of days (Working and Non-Working days).

The forecasts for each hour and day are then chronologically shorted to make a one-week-ahead forecast (168 hours). In cases where zero or negative forecasts occurred (mainly due to occasionally low quality of data) the calculated base load of the building is used to fill the missing forecasts.

Apart from weekends, local and national holidays, strikes can be considered as non-working days as long as a relevant feedback is available.

The update of the MLR model is performed similarly to Energy Production forecast MLR model.

2.2.3 Example: Sant Cugat Town Hall energy consumption

The MLR models of the Sant Cugat Town Hall were estimated using a training sample of almost 6 months (3426 hours of non-zero or missing data) from 17th April 2014 to 28th February 2015. The energy consumption data were collected by the on-site monitoring system of the Town Hall, while the weather data was stored in the database of a nearby weather station.

The proposed methodology achieved a good forecasting accuracy across the whole sample tested with insignificant bias to be detected. All the MLR models are mainly described through the equation given below

$$Energy\ consumption_{hour} = Constant + a * Dewpoint + b * Temperature + c * Month$$

The predicted (red line) and the original data (black line) are displayed in Figure 7 for 300 random observations of the sample.

Figure 7: The predicted (red line) and the original (black line) energy consumption for a random week (168 observations) of the Sant Cugat Town Hall data set.

2.2.4 Example: Zaanstad Town Hall energy consumption

In the case of the Zaanstad Town Hall, the energy consumption model is based on the same methodological approach described in sections 2.2.1 and 2.2.2. The MLR models were estimated using a training sample of almost 10.5 months (7539 hours of non-zero or missing data) from 1st June 2014 to 22th April 2015. The energy consumption data were collected by the on-site monitoring system of the Town Hall (9120 observations from 1st June 2014 to 16th June 2015), while the weather data by the database of a nearby weather station (8660 observations from 15th April 2014 to 22th April 2015). In practice, the inner join of the two previous sub-sets constructed the training sample of the energy prediction models.

The proposed methodology achieved a good forecasting accuracy across the whole sample tested (sMAPE=11.6%) with insignificant bias to be detected. All the MLR models were mainly described through the equations given below, for working and non-working days respectively

Energy consumption Working Days_{hour}

$$= \text{Constant} + a * \text{Temperature} + a * \text{Temperature}^2 + c * \text{Month} + d * \text{Dewpoint} + e * \text{Pressure} + f * \text{Day}$$

Energy consumption Non – Working Days_{hour}

$$= \text{Constant} + a * \text{Temperature} + a * \text{Temperature}^2 + c * \text{Month} + d * \text{Dewpoint} + e * \text{Day}$$

The predicted (red line) and the original data (black line) are displayed in Figure 8 for 168 random observations of the sample. We note that due to relative variances even between the groups of working and non-working days, possibly because of periodic timetables and programs, the *Day* itself (Monday, Tuesday...Sunday) was considered as an additional predictor to further boost the performance of the models.

Figure 8: The predicted (red line) and the original (black line) energy consumption for a random week (168 observations) of the Zaanstad Town Hall data set.

2.2.5 Example: Savona Campus energy consumption

The energy consumption model of the Savona Campus was also developed according to the methodology presented in the previous sections. The individual MLR models were estimated using a training sample of almost 4 months (3338 hours of non-zero or missing data) from 1st January 2014 to 22th April 2015. The energy consumption data were collected by the on-site monitoring system of the Campus (5783 observations from 1st January 2014 to 31st July 2015), while the weather data was stored in the database of a nearby weather station (8608 observations from 15th April 2014 to 22th April 2015). In practice, the inner join of the two previous sub-sets constructed the training sample of the energy prediction models.

Like the previous examples of sections 2.2.3 and 2.2.4, the proposed methodology achieved good forecasting accuracy (sMAPE=16.7%) across the whole sample tested with insignificant bias to be detected. The MLR models were mainly described through the equations given below, for working and non-working days respectively

Energy consumption Working Days_{hour}

$$= Constant + a * Temperature + a * Temperature^2 + c * Month + d * Dewpoint$$

Energy consumption Non – Working Days_{hour}

$$= Constant + a * Temperature + a * Temperature^2 + c * Month$$

The predicted (red line) and the original data (black line) are displayed in Figure 9 for 168 random observations of the sample.

Figure 9: The predicted (red line) and the original (black line) energy consumption for a random week (168 observations) of the Savona Campus data set.

2.2.6 Data required

Following the methodology presented in Section 2.2.1, a variety of primary predictors were collected to help us boost the forecasting performance of the MLR models. As a general case, these predictors were divided into primary and secondary ones. The first group includes weather, time and building's characteristics, while the second refers to powers and the inter-relation (products) of the primary ones.

Taking the above into consideration, a set of predictors were developed for the Sant Cugat and Zaanstad cases following a stepwise method. A list of the primary predictors that were considered per pilot building is given in Table 4, while the secondary ones arise accordingly.

Table 4: List of the primary predictors for the Sant Cugat Town Hall

Predictor	Measurement Unit	Source	Type of data
Outdoor temperature	°C	Weather station	Weather
Indoor temperature	°C	Monitoring system	De-centralized
Degree Days –Heating or Cooling	°C d	Monitoring system	Weather
Humidity	-	Weather station	Weather
Pressure	Pa	Weather station	Weather
Wind Direction Degrees	-	Weather station	Weather
Solar Radiation	W/m ²	Weather station	Weather
Dewpoint	C ⁰	Weather station	Weather
Wind Speed	km/h	Weather station	Weather
Month	-	DSS engine	Time
Hour	-	DSS engine	Time
Day	- (applicable only to the Zaanstad pilot)	DSS engine	Time
Type of day (Working-Non Working)	-	DSS engine	Time
Envelope Characteristics	-	DSS engine	Building profile
Occupancy profile	-	DSS engine	Building profile

As the table shows, the predictors refer not only to external weather data but also to variables closely related with the functions and the schedules of the examined building.

2.3 Prediction model for indoor temperature

2.3.1 Methodology

The prediction of the indoor air temperature is necessary for the implementation of the OPTIMUS DSS action plan aimed at setting an optimum start and stop of the heating system.

The method used for the prediction is based on a grey-box approach and on a lumped model with one thermal capacitance and one thermal resistance.

The model is characterized by a node representing the indoor air temperature (θ). This node is connected to the external temperature through a heat resistance while the thermal capacitance is placed in the internal node, as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Capacitance-resistance building model.

The indoor air temperature trends can be assumed similar to the ones shown in Figure 11(a) and (b), considering a cut-off or a set-back period respectively, in accordance to EN ISO 13790: 2004 (ISO, 2004).

Figure 11: Indoor air temperature trend for cut-off mode (a) and set-back mode (b).

The procedure to calculate the indoor air temperature for one week is the following:

1. The monitored indoor and outdoor air temperature is recorded with a sampling frequency of 1 hour together with the heating system operation schedule for each zone. The recording period should be at least as long as the entire heating season.
2. The data set period is divided into days and weeks considering the working days and the holidays.
3. The data set period is divided into the following sub-periods: 1) cut-off period; 2) boost period; 3) normal heating system operation period. See Figure 12. The DSS subdivides each period according to the scheduling of the heating system operation.

Figure 12: Indoor air temperature trend for cut-off mode.

4. Considering the monitored indoor air temperature in the cut-off period, τ and Φ_i/H coefficients are calculated by applying equation 1. Φ_i/H coefficient is the ratio between the total amount of the heat gain entering the zone (W) and the total heat transfer coefficient (W/K); τ is the time constant of the zone.

$$\frac{\theta_i - \left(\theta_e + \left(\frac{\Phi_i}{H} \right)_1 \right)}{\theta_{i0}^* - \left(\theta_e + \left(\frac{\Phi_i}{H} \right)_1 \right)} = e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}} \quad (1)$$

where

θ_i is the monitored indoor air temperature during the cut-off period;

θ_e is the average value of the hourly monitored outdoor air temperature calculated during the cut-off period;

θ_{i0} is the indoor air temperature at time (t) = 0 of the cut-off period.

Both terms (τ and Φ_i/H) are calculated as the parameters that solve the following equation:

$$\left[\frac{\theta_i - \left(\theta_e + \left(\frac{\Phi_i}{H} \right)_1 \right)}{\theta_{i0}^* - \left(\theta_e + \left(\frac{\Phi_i}{H} \right)_1 \right)} - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}} \right]^2 = 0 \quad (2)$$

The longer is the cut-off mode period, the higher will be the accuracy of the time constant of the zone.

5. Considering the monitored indoor air temperature of the boost, the Φ_i/H coefficient is calculated by applying equation 3:

$$\frac{\theta_i - \left(\theta_e + \left(\frac{\Phi_i}{H} \right)_2 \right)}{\theta_{i0}^* - \left(\theta_e + \left(\frac{\Phi_i}{H} \right)_2 \right)} = e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}} \quad (3)$$

where

θ_i is the monitored indoor air temperature during the boost period;

θ_e is the average value of the hourly monitored outdoor air temperature calculated during the boost period;

θ_0 is the indoor air temperature at time (t) = 0 of the boost period.

6. The same procedure is repeated for the remaining periods of the week. Once the parameters have been found, they are used for the prediction of the indoor air temperature of the week after, using the forecast outdoor air temperature.
7. The indoor air temperature of the next week is calculated considering, for each period, the following equation, where n is the number of the periods:

$$\theta_i = e^{-t/\tau} \cdot \left(\theta_{i,0,n} - \theta_{e,n} - \left(\frac{\Phi}{H} \right)_n \right) + \theta_{e,n} + \left(\frac{\Phi}{H} \right)_n \quad (4)$$

8. Once a week, the procedure is repeated in order to better calibrate the model.

2.3.2 Predictive model for indoor air temperature

The grey-box approach was applied to predict the indoor air temperature trend during the heating period.

The heating period was subdivided into cut-off period, boost period and normal heating period. For both cut-off and boost periods the regressors (τ and Φ/H) were found.

The methodology was applied for the entire heating season: for each weekends/holyday the time constant and Φ/H value were calculated; for each cut-off period and boost period different Φ/H values were calculated.

An average value of the time constant was found for the overall heating period. A correlation was found between Φ/H values and the average outdoor air temperature both for cut-off and boost periods (Figure 13). This correlation enables identifying a Φ/H value for the week after considering the forecast outdoor air temperature.

Figure 13: Correlation between Φ/H values and outdoor air temperature for cut-off and boost mode.

2.3.3 Example: Sant Cugat Town Hall indoor temperature

The indoor air temperature prediction model was first applied to the Sant Cugat Town Hall using the collected data of 4 months of the heating period between 2014 and 2015. The indoor air temperature was collected for one zone of the Town Hall (Zone 1(A) – CZ1.1 – F3 in Figure 14) while the outdoor air temperature was collected from a nearby weather station.

Figure 14: Plan of the third floor of Sant Cugat Town Hall with the building partitioning referred to the monitored zones.

The indoor air temperature trend is characterized by an evident cut-off period (both during weekend and weekdays) and boost period (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Example of indoor air temperature trend for each day of a week.

Considering the trend of indoor air temperature in the cut off periods during weekend, the time constant of the zone was calculated and average values were considered for the entire heating period ($\tau = 17$ h). Moreover, Φ/H values were calculated based on the indoor air temperature in the cut off and the boost periods during the weekdays.

The predicted indoor air temperature for the week after was predicted using the time constant and the Φ/H values correlated to the forecasted outdoor air temperature as identified in Figure 13.

An example of validation is given in Figure 16. Only the boost and the cut-off modes were validated. The average deviation between the monitored and the predicted datum is $0,21^{\circ}\text{C}$; the maximum deviation is $0,5^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Figure 16: Comparison between monitored and predicted indoor air temperature for a week of January 2015

2.3.4 Data required

The data needed for the model are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: List of the primary predictors for the Sant Cugat Town Hall.

Predictor	Measurement Unit	Source	Type of data
Outdoor temperature	°C	Weather station	Weather
Indoor temperature	°C	Monitoring system	De-centralized
Month	-	DSS engine	Time
Day	-	DSS engine	Time
Hour	-	DSS engine	Time
Type of day (Working-Non Working)	-	DSS engine	Time
On/off of the heating system scheduling	-	DSS engine	Building profile

2.4 Prediction model for energy prices

2.4.1 Methodology

Depending on the action plans implemented in a pilot building, a prediction of both the energy prices for the upcoming week and the relevant energy cost might be required. In other action plans, however, it might be enough to know when the energy price is cheaper.

Forecasting relies on the prices provided by the energy markets in the countries where the pilot buildings are located, namely OMIE (Operador del Mercado Ibérico de la Energía) in Spain and GME (Gestore dei Mercati Energetici) in Italy.

The prediction of the energy prices is done following these steps:

- *Step 1:* A service is used for capturing historical data of energy prices.
- *Step 2:* A prediction model forecasts their value for the upcoming week.
- *Step 3:* After calculating the predicted values, the relevant energy cost of the pilot building is estimated.

The frequency of the captured data (e.g. hourly or daily) and the forecasting horizon (e.g. one week or month ahead) require a different prediction models in the pilot buildings. Specifically, two different prediction models have been devised to meet the requirements of the pilot cases in Sant Cugat (Spain) and Savona (Italy), as follows:

- The first model, which is applicable to the Sant Cugat buildings pilots, uses a 6th degree polynomial technique to extrapolate the historical prices and then applies the charges to the predicted energy consumption data, in order to estimate the final energy cost. The historical data in this case have hourly frequency.
- The second prediction model, which is applicable to the Savona pilots (Colombo-Pertini School and Savona Campus), uses an exponential smoothing method for predicting the monthly energy prices per charging zone (see section 2.4.2). This model is based on the following assumptions:
 - The price of each charging zone is calculated with the mean price of electricity within the month and the zone.
 - The price becomes publicly available at the beginning of the next month.

For the Italian pilots, there is no need for calculating the bill of energy since the action plans operating in this case (e.g. AP7 - Scheduling the operation of heating and electricity systems towards optimal use of cogeneration technology) only require the hours in which the electricity is cheaper rather than its exact cost. Therefore, the billing formula takes into consideration other factors that might influence the prices (such as peaks) which might be useful to optimize the energy flows. ~~It is also noted that, although the action plans implemented in the School do not require the prediction of energy prices, the same model could be used if needed given that the School and the Campus have the same electricity provider.~~

2.4.2 Predictive models for energy prices

Both energy prices prediction models follow a black box model. This means that the prediction of the energy prices is going to be based on measured data, which in this case correspond to known market prices, rather than in the knowledge of single factors, such as weather data, local regulations, etc. In Spain, the day ahead regulator is OMIE that deals with Spanish and Portuguese electricity markets, while the Italian regulator is GME. From each provider, historical data are collected on daily basis and given as input to the corresponding prediction model. The billing policy also differs in each prediction model and different functions are used for estimating the cost, if needed. The two prediction models are described in detail as follows:

Sant Cugat pilot cases

For the case of the Spanish pilot cases (Town Hall and Theatre), the 6th degree polynomial prediction model is first used for forecasting hourly energy prices and then the bill is calculated based on the charging mechanism of the electricity provider and the forecasted prices, energy consumption and production.

More specifically, the electricity supplier applies the following formula to calculate the electricity bill:

$$Te_i = PMAM_i + B_i \left(\frac{\text{€}}{MWh} \right)$$

where:

$PMAM_i$ is the hourly average energy cost for the billing month regarding to Spanish regulation OTC/3801/2008:

B_i is the correction factor for the hourly cost average:

- $B_i = ((Pc_i + Rt_i + Sc_i + OS_i + OM_i) * (1 + \%Perd_i)) + ATR_i + Com_i$ (€)
 - (Pc): Payments for system capacity
 - (Rt+Sc): Restriction techniques and complementary services
 - (OS+OM): Market and other costs
 - (ATR): Energy taxes
 - (%Perd) Coefficient for losses annually calculated and extrapolated to each month.
 - (Com): Other costs, taxes and deviations due to the consumption pattern change.

The billing formula is based on the market prices for electricity and it includes a corrective factor which takes into consideration taxes, energy losses and additional costs.

However, in order to estimate the cost the formula described above must be applied in two cases: (i) for the previous month and (ii) for the previous billing period. The billing period may correspond to a year or a month, and it may, in some cases, include more than one month (i.e. from January to March) or days that belong to different months (i.e. from the 15th of month#1 to the 15th of month#2). Therefore, in order to deal with most of the possible situations, both options are considered.

In order to estimate hourly energy cost (e.g. price), the historical data are grouped in different periods considering energy consumption, as shown in Figure 17. The average price of the energy of these periods is applied in next billing period in the same charging zones. Therefore, the final prices depend directly on the data delivered by OMIE. Then the polynomial technique is used to extrapolate their values.

Figure 17: Charging zones of the Sant Cugat.

A polynomial technique is a mathematical representation of a curve by means of an n degree polynomial function. A curve with infinite radius is a line, which is a first-degree polynomial. A second-degree polynomial represents a parabola, and so on. From the analysis and study of the daily values for the day ahead energy prices it is possible to conclude that they can be accurately approached to a sixth degree polynomial (Figure 18).

Figure 18: Energy prices and 6th degree polynomial.

The set of charts and equations represented above describe the matching between the energy prices evolution within a day and the polynomial approach.

- The equation representing the orange curve in the chart is:
 $y = -9E-05x^6 + 0,0063x^5 - 0,1652x^4 + 2,0353x^3 - 11,916x^2 + 31,166x - 16,855$
- The equation representing the blue curve in the chart is:
 $y = -2E-05x^6 + 0,0009x^5 + 0,0024x^4 - 0,5408x^3 + 8,0593x^2 - 36,532x + 54,332$

Savona pilot cases

In the case of the Italian pilot cases (School and Campus), the buildings buy energy at times having different price depending on the time zone (F1, F2 and F3) and the type of day (Sunday, Saturday and Monday-Friday) as shown in Figure 19. This means that although the zones are standard, their price might vary within the year. F3 is always the cheapest (weekends, night and holidays, when energy consumption is minimal). F2 is usually cheaper than F1, because energy demand is increased within zone F1. However, this is not always the case since at some rare occasions, and especially in summer time, the power consumption of each zone vary and F1 may be cheaper than F2. This is why energy prices forecasting becomes essential.

Figure 19: Charging zones of the Savona Campus.

The price of the energy at each zone (PriceF1, PriceF2, PriceF3) is calculated every month based on the mean daily energy price of the zone (F1, F2, F3) and type of day (Sunday, Saturday, Monday-Friday) and the bill is calculated, if needed, by the following formula:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Energy Cost} = & [91,65 \\
 & +1,04 \times \text{EnergyF1} \times \text{PriceF1} \\
 & +1,04 \times \text{EnergyF2} \times \text{PriceF2} \\
 & +1,04 \times \text{EnergyF3} \times \text{PriceF3} \\
 & +2,74 \times \text{Peak (monthly)} \\
 & + (0,00988 + 0,09117) \times \text{TotalEnergy} + 0,0151 \times 4,66174 \times \text{TotalEnergy}/100] \times 1,22
 \end{aligned}$$

→ Fixed Cost
 } Energy Consumption Cost
 → Peak Penalty

Losses

As seen, the bill includes a fixed cost, a cost based on total electricity consumption and losses, a cost based on the electricity consumed per charging zone and a peak penalty.

Since the implemented action plans in the Italian pilots optimize energy costs by decreasing peaks and shifting loads to cheaper zones, the forecasting model is limited to predict the difference between F1 and F2 which are the cheapest zones for the upcoming month (there is no need of predicting F3 since it is always the cheapest and available at times when buildings are not occupied). Predicting the difference of two zones helps to produce more robust and accurate forecasts providing that, although prices might be volatile, their difference might follow a certain pattern.

More specifically, the difference between the energy prices is forecasted using exponential smoothing models (Hyndman et al. 2002). These models (27 in total) use smoothing techniques to identify and extrapolate trends and seasonal patterns in time series. They are a powerful technique to deal with fast moving data and noisy time series and they are reliable enough for short-term forecasts like in our case (one month ahead). Monthly historical data are used for training the available models. The most accurate is selected by minimizing the mean squared error and then used for predicting. The model can be easily expanded to

multiple step-ahead forecasts. For example, if the coming week encompasses days of the current and following month, a two step-ahead forecast will be required.

Figure 20: Italian mean (monthly) electricity prices from 1-1-2011 to 1-2-2016.

2.4.3 Example: Sant Cugat Town Hall and Theatre energy prices

For the case of the Sant Cugat pilots, the energy prices prediction model has been implemented in PHP as an algorithm that depends directly on data fetched by the energy prices capturing module described in Deliverable 2.5. Then, based on the billing formula described in previous sections, the final energy cost can be estimated. The implementation of the energy prices forecasting model is based on an iterative application of polynomial techniques.

Figure 21: Prediction Model for Sant Cugat.

Figure 21 shows the sequence of actions in the prediction model of the Sant Cugat Town Hall. It should be noticed that the billing in Sant Cugat is per month, while the predictions made by the OPTIMUS DSS are per week. The predictions made by the OPTIMUS DSS will support the deployment of corrective actions and prevent consumption deviations due to unexpected energy demands.

2.4.4 Data required

Both day-ahead market regulators – OMIE and GME – provide free access to daily energy prices for the next 24 hours. The outcomes of the daily bids are public, even though the price establishment process is private for the market participants.

The access to day-ahead markets is free, even though in the case of the Italian market a registration process is required. The Italian regulator GME provides access towards an FTP server, while the Spanish regulator OMIE provides the information in a web page.

Table 6: Access to Italian and Spanish energy market data

Day Ahead Market	Free Access	Registration need	Access type
Italian	YES	YES	FTP server
Spanish	YES	NO	HTTP site, Plain text

The data required to feed the prediction models are the energy prices provided by the energy markets for the next 24 hours, in periods of 1 hour. However, the day-ahead prices are not always available 24 hours in advance. In order to prevent the lack of forecast due to the delay in the availability of energy prices data, the prediction model will deliver a temporary forecast as soon as the energy price become available.

3 Prediction models implementation

The prediction models connect the semantic framework with the inference rules. The prediction models take both, historical and monitored data from the semantic framework (described in Deliverable 3.1) to forecast the building behaviour. The predicted data is used by the inference rules to suggest action plans. A comprehensive description of the inference rules can be found in D3.3 *Inference engine integrated in the management environments*.

The prediction models have been published as web services using RapidAnalytics¹ that is a data mining open source tool. The prediction models have been encapsulated as RapidMiner processes which facilitate the communication between the semantic framework and the inference rules.

3.1 Renewable energy production and energy consumption prediction models

The implementation of the prediction models for renewable energy production and energy consumption is similar. The only difference is the input data and R scripts that are used to calculate the models. The models consist of two RapidMiner processes: 1) to train a prediction model with historical data, and 2) to apply the previous model with monitored data to forecast.

3.1.1 Creating the prediction model

The RapidMiner process to train a prediction model involves three main operators (Figure 22):

1. **Open file.** This operator gets through the semantic service historical data for training the model. It invokes a GET HTML call with the starting date and the number of records. An example of this call could be: `/semantic_service/get_data_for_model/production/2015-03-03T00:00:00Z/2160` where *production* is the type of prediction model, the *2015-03-03T00:00:00Z* is the starting date, and *2160* is the number of records (3 months of data). After data is retrieved, it is processed with the Read CSV operator.
2. **Execute script.** This operator encapsulates the “R script” for training the prediction model. It receives the data processed by the previous operator. The outputs of the “execute script” are the forecasted data made with the trained model and the model itself.
3. **Store.** This operator receives the model trained in the previous operator and stores it in the RapidMiner repository for its later use in other processes.

¹ <http://sourceforge.net/projects/rapidanalytics/>

Figure 22: Process for training a prediction model based on an R script.

3.1.2 Applying the prediction model

The RapidMiner process to apply the prediction model with monitored data encompasses four main operators (Figure 23):

1. **Open file.** This operator asks the semantic service monitored data for applying the model. It invokes a GET HTML call with the starting date and the number of records to be forecasted. An example of this call could be: `/semantic_service/get_data_for_forecasting/production/2015-03-03T00:00:00Z/168` where *production* is the type of prediction model, the *2015-03-03T00:00:00Z* is the starting date, and *168* is the number of records (7 days of data). After data is retrieved, it is processed with the Read CSV operator.
2. **Retrieve.** This operator loads from the RapidMiner repository the prediction model trained with the previous process.
3. **Execute script.** This operator encapsulates the “R script” for forecasting the data by applying the prediction model. It receives the data processed by the previous operator and the prediction model. The output of the “Execute script” is the forecasted data.
4. **Select Attribute.** This operator selects the main attributes that will be the outputs. The selected attributes are the prediction and the timestamp.

Figure 23: Process for applying a prediction model based on an R script.

3.2 Indoor temperature prediction model

The prediction model is based on the grey box approach and it is applied to calculate the predicted indoor temperature of a building zone. The prediction model has been completely developed as a RapidMiner process without any external coding.

The model implementation is based on the identification of the cut-off mode and of boost periods for each day. Later, the equation 1 is applied for each period:

$$\frac{\theta_i - \left(\theta_e + \left(\frac{\Phi_i}{H} \right)_1 \right)}{\theta_{i0}^* - \left(\theta_e + \left(\frac{\Phi_i}{H} \right)_1 \right)} = e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}} \quad (1)$$

where:

θ_i is the monitored indoor air temperature.

θ_e is the average value of the hourly monitored outdoor air temperature calculated during the cut-off mode.

θ_{i0} is the indoor air temperature at time (t) = 0 of the cut-off mode.

τ is the time constant.

Φ_i/H is the ratio between the total amount of the heat gain entering the zone (W) and the total heat transfer coefficient (W/K).

The goal of the prediction model is to forecast the time constant (τ) parameter and Φ_i/H coefficients based on the historical data (e.g., weather conditions, indoor temperature, and occupancy). The model consists of two RapidMiner processes: 1) to train a prediction model with historical data, and 2) to apply the previous model with monitored data to forecast.

3.2.1 Creating the prediction model

The goal of the RapidMiner process that trains a prediction model is to obtain the time constant and Φ_i/H coefficients for the cut-off and boost periods using historical data of the days that the heating system has been used. It is composed of three main sub-processes (Figure 24):

1. **Get Data Divide Periods.** The goal is to obtain the historical data, to divide it in weeks, and to identify the cut-off and boost periods.
2. **Loop Weeks.** The goal is to loop for each week and to find the time constant parameter for the week and the Φ_i/H coefficients for the cut-off and boost periods.
3. **Build MLRs.** The goal is to build three Linear Regressor Model (MLR) to relate the outdoor temperature with the Φ_i/H coefficients for the cut-off (weekends and weekdays) and boost periods.

Figure 24: Process for creating the prediction model for indoor temperature.

3.2.1.1 Get Data Divide Periods sub-process

This sub-process is divided into three steps: getting data, identifying cut-off and boost periods, and clustering data into weeks (Figure 25).

1. **Getting data.** The data is retrieved from the DSS. The data needed to run this sub-process are the indoor temperature, outdoor temperatures, and the occupation of the building.
2. **Identifying periods.** The goal is to find the cut-off and boost periods and to identify between the cut-off periods of the weekdays and weekends. This is important because the cut-off period of the weekends is used to calculate the time constant parameter. The cut-off periods occur when the indoor temperature is steadily decreasing. They could have small boost periods but these are skipped. The boost periods are those ones in which the indoor temperature is increasing for several hours. The cut-off periods are divided into those that last less than 12 hours (weekdays), and those lasting more than 12 hours (weekends).
3. **Clustering in weeks.** In this step, the data is clustered in weeks using the date attribute of the input data.

Figure 25: Sub-process for finding the cut-off and boost periods for each week.

3.2.1.2 Loop week sub-process

In this case, there is an iteration each week to find the time constant parameter and the Φ_i/H coefficients for the cut-off and boost periods. This sub-process is carried out for each week of the historical data. It applies the equation 1 to calculate the time constant and the Φ_i/H coefficients (Figure 26).

1. **Calculating the time constant.** The time constant is calculated only using the cut-off of the weekend period. The equation 1 is applied for the period by testing different pairs of values for the time constant and Φ_i/H coefficient. The range of values tested for the time constant is between 15 and 30. The range for the Φ_i/H coefficient is between 5 and 30. For each pair of values, the indoor temperature is calculated which is later compared with the monitored one using the mean square error estimator. The pair of values with the minimum square error is selected.
2. **Calculating the Φ_i/H coefficients.** The calculation of Φ_i/H coefficients for the cut-off (weekdays) and boost periods is similar to the previous procedure. In this case, the time constant has been already calculated and it is the same for all the periods. In this case the equation 1 is applied for each period by testing different values of the Φ_i/H coefficient. The indoor temperature calculated is compared with the monitored one using a mean square error estimator. The Φ_i/H value with the minimum square error is selected.

Figure 26: Sub-process for finding the time constant and Φ_i/H coefficients.

The output of this process is a list of the time constant parameter for each week and a list of Φ_i/H coefficient for each cut-off and boost periods of the weeks.

3.2.1.3 Build MLRs sub-process

The purpose of this task is to build three Linear Regressor Models (MLR) to relate the outdoor temperature with the Φ_i/H coefficients for the cut-off weekend period, cut-off weekdays periods, and boost periods. The input of this sub-process is a list of Φ_i/H coefficients calculated in the previous sub-process.

The data for the weekends periods (1) and weekdays periods (2) is processed and then three linear regression models are calculated (3, 4, 5). Those models are stored in the RapidMiner repository for its later use.

Figure 27: Sub-process for building the MLR models.

3.2.2 Applying the prediction model

The purpose of the RapidMiner process is to calculate the indoor temperature using the equation 1 for one week in the future. The parameters needed - such as the time constant and Φ_i/H coefficients- are forecasted using the models calculated in the process “Creating the model” described in Section 3.2.1 of this document.

The process is divided into two sub-processes, one to analyse the input data, and the other one to predict the indoor temperature (Figure 28).

1. **Get Data Prediction.** In this sub-process, the data needed (outdoor temperature, occupation, temperature set point) for forecasting the indoor temperature is retrieved from the DSS. From the input data, the cut-off and boost periods are identified.
2. **Predict temperature.** The goal of this sub-process is to forecast Φ_i/H coefficients based on the input data and the MLR models already created.

Figure 28: Process for applying the prediction model to forecast indoor temperature.

3.2.2.1 Get Data Prediction sub-process

The goal of this task is to obtain the input data from the DSS and to identify the cut-off and boost periods using the occupation profile. The periods are identified using simple heuristics.

- From Friday to Monday, after the building is closed → cut-off period for weekends
- From Monday to Thursday, after the building is closed and before 2 am of the next day → cut-off period for weekdays.
- From Monday to Friday, from 2 am to the building is opened → boost period.
- From Monday to Friday, when the building is opened → normal heating period.

3.2.2.2 Predict temperature sub-process

The goal of this sub-process is to forecast Φ_i/H coefficients based on the input data analysed in the previous sub-process and the MLR models already created and stored in the RapidMiner repository. The sub-process encompasses three kinds of routines (Figure 29):

1. **Forecast Φ_i/H coefficients.** These routines use a specific MLR model to predict the Φ_i/H coefficients for each period (cut-off weekends, cut-off weekdays, and boost) based on the input data, mainly with the average of the outdoor temperature of the period.
2. **Calculate Time constant.** This routine calculates the time constant using the input data. The process is the same as the one described in Section 3.2.1.2 “Loop week sub-process”.
3. **Predict indoor temperature.** This routine takes the input data, the time constant and Φ_i/H coefficients calculated in the previous routines to apply the equation 1.

Figure 29: Sub-process for predicting the indoor-temperature.

3.3 Energy prices prediction models

As described in section 2.4, two different prediction models have been devised one for the Sant Cugat pilot cases (using a polynomial technique) and one for Savona cases (using a smoothing technique).

More specifically, for the Sant Cugat pilot buildings a 6th degree polynomial is used for predicting the energy prices and then the billing function of the energy provider is applied for calculating total energy cost. The prediction model has been implemented as PHP classes. Unlike other prediction models described above, in this case there is no separation between creating the prediction model and applying it to forecast data.

For the Savona pilot cases an exponential smoothing model is used for predicting energy prices per charging zone. There is no direct calculation of the total energy cost in this case. If needed, an ex post estimation of the cost can be performed within a particular action plan (e.g. AP7) using the forecasts produced by the model and the charging function of the provider. Like the rest of the prediction models, in this case the model is selected, trained and applied to the historical data using an R script available as a RapidMiner web service.

3.3.1 Prediction model for the Sant Cugat pilot cases

The energy prices of the previous month are used to predict the upcoming week energy prices. These prices are grouped in different time periods. The energy prices average of these periods is performed and the result is used to calculate the next week prices forecast. The periods are divided taking into consideration the following:

- Type of day: working days (weekdays) and non-working days (weekends-holidays).
- Time zone: F1, F2, F3
- Season: Winter or Summer.

Table 7: Different periods for prices prediction model, Sant Cugat case.

From Monday to Friday		
	Winter	Summer
Period 1	00h-08h	00h-08h
Period 2	08h-18h	08h-11h
Period 3	18h-22h	11h-15h
Period 4	22h-24h	15h-24h
From Saturday to Sunday		
	Winter	Summer
Period 1	00h-08h	00h-08h
Period 2	08h-18h	08h-11h
Period 3	18h-22h	11h-15h
Period 4	22h-24h	15h-24h

The main methods invoked by the prediction model are the following:

1. **Get data database.** This method requests monitored data to the semantic service for applying the model, taking as reference the OMIE (Spanish Market regulator) prices. It invokes a GET HTML with the starting date and ending date of the previous month of the week whose prices will be forecasted.
2. **Next week energy price prediction.** Given the prices of the previous month, prices of the next week are predicted.

Figure 30: Classes included in the prediction model to forecast Sant Cugat and Italian pilot buildings energy prices.

The energy price prediction model has been implemented with PHP classes. Figure 30 shows the relation between the different PHP classes which have been created to implement this prediction model.

The model and its respective classes are described in the following sections.

3.3.1.1 Get data database: Collection and aggregation of historical data

Class ServicePeriodEvaluator: Function Evaluate

The purpose of this class is to calculate the energy prices average in the previous month for every day in the period indicated in Table 7. The result is a two-dimensional array with every day of the month and three time zones (F1, F2 and F3) for which the daily average price is saved.

Class ServicePeriodEvaluator: Function CalculateAveragePerDayType

The goal is to calculate the energy price average of different type of day (all weekdays and all weekends-holidays) in the three time zones. The result is a two-dimensional array containing the average prices for different type of day of the three time zones.

3.3.1.2 Next week energy price prediction: Prediction model based on a 6th degree polynomial technique

The energy prices prediction model is based on a 6th degree polynomial technique that is different for each predicted day:

- Monday-Saturday: A polynomial regression model calculated with previous week workdays data is used.
- Sunday: A regression model using previous Sunday data is used.

Figure 31 shows the relation between the different classes which have been created for this prediction model.

Figure 31: Classes included in the prediction model based on a 6th degree polynomial technique.

Class ServicePolynomialEvaluator: Function Evaluate

The purpose of this class is to calculate the 6th degree polynomial regression models with the previous data. The result is a two-dimensional array with seven coefficients for the polynomial corresponding to Monday-Saturday and with seven coefficients for the polynomial for Sunday.

Class ServicePeriodEvaluator: Function GetNextDayForecast

This class implements the functionalities to calculate the next day price prediction using a 6th degree polynomial.

Class ServicePeriodEvaluator: Function GetNextWeekForecast

From the two-dimensional array that contains all prices, the prices corresponding to the week for which the prices are to be predicted are collected. The result is two-dimensional array containing the prices of every day in a week.

3.3.2 Prediction model for Savona pilot cases

For the Italian pilot cases, like the rest of the prediction models, energy prices are predicted through a RapidMiner service. The service collects historical data of energy prices and aggregates them on monthly basis so that the average price per charging zone is calculated. The monthly data are then imported in an R script which calculates the difference between the prices of zones F1 and F2 and selects the most appropriate exponential smoothing model for extrapolating according to the forecasting horizon chosen. The prediction indicates which zone is expected to be cheaper in the upcoming month and is exploited in the corresponding action plans.

At present, the stream of the data is connected to a static file. However, as soon as a real-time data stream becomes available the model will be collecting updates of energy prices per charging zone automatically at the beginning of each month.

The price periods are divided taking into consideration the following:

- Type of day: Working days (weekdays), Saturday and Sunday or holidays.
- Time zone: F1, F2, F3.

As a results the stream should be able to aggregate hourly energy prices per charging zone and month and provide the data required to the model. In this regard, PHP classes like the ones used for the case of the Sant Cugat buildings could be created for collecting and aggregating historical data as follows:

- Class ServicePeriodEvaluator: Function Evaluate
- Class ServicePeriodEvaluator: Function CalculateAveragePerDayType

Table 8: Different periods for prices prediction model, Italian pilot buildings case.

	Monday-Friday	Saturday	Sunday
F3	00h-07h	00h-07h	0h-24h
F2	07h-8h	07h-23h	
F1	8h-19h		
F2	19h-23h		
F3	23h-24h	23h-24h	

4 Conclusions

The prediction models are key components of the OPTIMUS DSS since they enable to forecast the energy performance of buildings and take measures to optimize it. Four prediction models have been developed for renewable energy production, energy consumption, indoor temperature, and energy prices.

Prediction models cannot be generalised; each application case has to be treated specifically. The prediction models are strongly related to the available input data. Therefore, models for predicting the same indicator with different input data required different strategies. We have outlined the theoretical grounds to create prediction models with the available data in the pilot cases. This methodology can be used to develop new prediction models, applicable to other cases.

The prediction models will be verified in the demonstration scenarios. They will be tuned and enhanced with the feedback gathered during their application in the pilot cases.

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